

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS OF AN ASYNCHRONOUS ELECTRIC MOTOR USING THE MULTIPARAMETRIC DESIGN METHOD

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ABSTRACT

The subject of this study is a methodology for obtaining (synthesizing) the main attributes of an electromechanical energy converter, using an asynchronous electric motor as an example. This article examines an approach to organizing the calculation and modeling of the main attributes of an asynchronous electric motor. It demonstrates that considering multi-physical parameters, such as electrodynamic, mechanical, and thermal properties, improves the design quality both functionally and intellectually. The mathematical apparatus of the study is based on the parametric design of power machines. The synthesis resulted in design information on the main operating parameters of an asynchronous electric motor, which is sufficient for selecting a motor model from the manufacturer's catalog for subsequent use in design work.

Keywords: power machine, electrodynamic, mechanical and thermal processes, electric motor, synthesis of design.

Statement of the problem

The process of designing electromechanical energy converters is a complex and multifaceted task, which, on the one hand, is limited by the technical and methodological capabilities of the existing design tools, and on the other hand, by the modern requirements of the market for electromechanical equipment, which include the requirements of manufacturability, safety, environmental friendliness and reasonable economy of the future unit. Currently, known design methods are based on the sequential organization of calculation stages, followed by the process of modeling individual phenomena and effects of the functioning of the electric machine and modeling, at the final stage, the future design of the electromechanical energy converter. This approach affects both the timing of design work and the quality of individual results obtained as a result of design [1]. At the current stage of development of electrical engineering, the most actively used methodology of design work using computer-aided design systems (Computer-aided design, i.e. CAD). The mechanism of implementation of these systems is carried out by various methods, methods and models. Calculations in CAD are mostly performed by the following methods [2-5]:

- finite element method;
- finite difference method;
- finite volume method;
- boundary element method, etc.

CAD systems allow modeling of the solid-state structure of an electric machine taking into account the influence of electromagnetic, mechanical, hydraulic and thermal loads on it, which as a result makes it possible to obtain the value of the real design of the electromechanical converter for the subsequent manufacturing process and its assembly at an industrial site.

The quality requirements of electrical power equipment determine the following strategy for the development of the design of electromechanical energy converters [6]:

- use of case insulation and winding insulation of reduced thickness, including to achieve an increase in the coefficient of groove filling with copper and more rational use of the total volume of the machine;
- use of modern materials for electrical insulation, which have an increased class of heating resistance (class F and H);
- use of improved grades of electrical steel with increased magnetic permeability and lower loss rates;
- increase in the cooling efficiency of the electric machine by improving the gas path for cooling the core, winding, rotor and housing as a whole and improving the design and operating mode of fans and gas coolers (air coolers);
- rejection of hydrogen cooling medium (in powerful generators) and use of air agent for cooling the electric machine;
- reduction of the mass and dimensions of the structural elements of the electric machine (housing, shields, bearings, etc.);
- development and further use of typical solutions to improve manufacturability in production, to reduce specific costs at the production stage;
- improvement of the mathematical apparatus of CAD systems to increase the accuracy of the results obtained and reduce the timing of design and engineering work.

Research goals and objectives

The aim of the work is to synthesize the main attributes of an asynchronous electric motor using the multiparametric design method of power machines. The obtained data should contain design information sufficient to select a brand of power machine for further use in design work.

Material and essence of the research

1. Mathematical modeling

An induction motor (AM) is usually described in two complementary forms: through a steady-state-matched equivalent circuit (for steady-state modes and frequency characteristics) and through a coordinate transformation in dq for dynamics, control, and transients. The generalized equation of the phase frequency resistance of the stator $Z_s(\omega)$ and the rotor $Z_r(\omega)$ of an induction motor, in complex form, has the following form:

$$\begin{cases} Z_s(\omega) = R_s + j \cdot \omega \cdot L_{\sigma s}, \\ Z_r(\omega) = \frac{R_r}{s} + j \cdot \omega \cdot L_{\sigma r}; \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where, R_s and R_r are the active resistance of the stator and rotor, respectively, Ohm; $L_{\sigma r}$ and $L_{\sigma s}$ are the inductive dissipation index of the rotor and stator, respectively, Hn; j – an imaginary unit for the complex representation of phase shifts; ω – the angular frequency of the electrical network, Hz; s – the rotor slip, a.u.

Then the electromagnetic moment of the AM in the coordinates ω and s is equal to:

$$M_e(\omega, s) = \frac{3}{\omega_s} \cdot \frac{R_r}{s \cdot \left(\frac{R_r}{s}\right)^2 + \left(\omega \cdot L_{\sigma r} + \frac{\omega \cdot L_m \cdot Z_s}{Z_s + j \cdot \omega \cdot L_m}\right)^2} \cdot \Phi_e^2; \quad (2)$$

where, ω_s – angular frequency of the stator electric field, Hz; L_m – magnetizing inductance of the AM, Hn; Φ_e – effective flux linkage, in a simplified model the moment is classically written through the “moment” characteristic of the rotor with a magnetic component in parallel, a.u.

In addition to the electromagnetic moment of the AM, we present a system of flux linkage equations in dq -coordinates to take into account the dynamic component of the multiparametric model:

$$\begin{cases} u_{sd} = R_s \cdot i_{sd} + \frac{d\psi_{sd}}{dt} - \omega_s \cdot \psi_{sq}, \\ u_{sq} = R_s \cdot i_{sq} + \frac{d\psi_{sq}}{dt} + \omega_s \cdot \psi_{sd}, \\ 0 = R_r \cdot i_{rd} + \frac{d\psi_{sr}}{dt} - \omega_{sl} \cdot \psi_{rq}, \\ 0 = R_r \cdot i_{rq} + \frac{d\psi_{rq}}{dt} + \omega_{sl} \cdot \psi_{rd}; \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where, u_{sd} and u_{sq} – the voltage of the stator of the AM in the coordinates dq , V; i_{sd} and i_{sq} – the current of the stator of the AM in the coordinates dq , A; ψ_{sd} and ψ_{sq} – the index of the flux linkage of the stator of the AM in the coordinates dq , a.u.; ψ_{rd} and ψ_{rq} – the index of the flux linkage of the rotor of the AM in the coordinates dq , a.u. $\omega_{sl} = \omega_s - \omega_r$ – the slip frequency,

which is equal to the difference between the frequency of the electromagnetic field of the stator and the frequency of mechanical rotation of the rotor, Hz.

In this case, the relationship between currents and flux linkage of the AC can be formulated as follows [7]:

$$\begin{cases} i_{sd} = \frac{\psi_{sd} - \frac{L_m}{L_{\sigma r}} \cdot \psi_{rd}}{L_{\sigma s} + \frac{L_m^2}{L_{\sigma r}}}, & i_{sq} = \frac{\psi_{sq} - \frac{L_m}{L_{\sigma r}} \cdot \psi_{rq}}{L_{\sigma s} + \frac{L_m^2}{L_{\sigma r}}}, \\ i_{rd} = \frac{\psi_{rd} - \frac{L_m}{L_{\sigma s}} \cdot \psi_{sd}}{L_{\sigma r} + \frac{L_m^2}{L_{\sigma s}}}, & i_{rq} = \frac{\psi_{rq} - \frac{L_m}{L_{\sigma s}} \cdot \psi_{sq}}{L_{\sigma r} + \frac{L_m^2}{L_{\sigma s}}}; \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

When designing an AM with the ability to use multiparameterization properties, the variables become geometry, materials, connection schemes, types of cooling, restrictions on electric current density and electric load. Therefore, the expression M_e must be represented with a dependence on the vector of parameters

$$p = f(R_c, N_s, N_r, d_s, l_s, \mu(B, \omega), \sigma_{cu}(T, \omega), \sigma_{al}(T, \omega), d_{sp}, d_{rp}, b_r, b_s, h_r, h_s, g, L_m, \dots) \quad (5)$$

a) electrical parameters:

p and include both electromechanical and additional elements (multiphysical). The composition of the vector may vary depending on the purpose and conditions of the real project, but in the basic value it must contain the following information blocks, according to the expression below:

R_c – equivalent electrical energy losses of the stator core, W;

d_s and l_s – diameter and length of the stator core, m;

N_s , and N_r – number of turns / rods of the stator and rotor winding, pcs.

b) parameters of the properties of the structural material:

$\mu(B, \omega)$ – complex magnetic permeability of the core material, which depends on the frequency of the electric current, H/m;

$\sigma_{Cu}(T, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{Al}(T, \omega)$ – electrical conductivity of copper and aluminum of the stator and rotor windings, Cm.

d_{sp} and d_{rp} – diameter of the wire from which the stator and rotor windings are made, m.

c) geometric parameters:

b_r and b_s – width of the rotor and stator slot, respectively, m;

h_r and h_s – depth of the rotor and stator slot, respectively, m;

g – width of the air gap between the inner diameter of the stator and the outer diameter of the rotor, m.

d) electromagnetic indicators:

L_m – inductance of the magnetizing component of the AM, a.u.

Table 1 shows a comparison of information blocks (variables) with the characteristics of their influence on the AM.

Table 1

Correlation of information variables with the characteristics of their influence on an asynchronous electric motor

Parameter	Impact on asynchronous electric motor
R_c	Determines the efficiency index, the degree of core heating, the amount of frequency losses
d_s and l_s	Limits the electromagnetic flux and the shape of the magnetic field, influences the magnitude of the electromechanical moment, determines the losses of electrical energy, and greatly affects the mass index of the AM.
N_s , and N_r	Mainly determines the EMF, forms the flux, affects the magnetizing inductance of the core
$\mu(B, \omega)$	Determines the inductance of the active zone of the AM and affects electrical energy losses
$\sigma_{Cu}(T, \omega)$ $\sigma_{Al}(T, \omega)$	Determine the active losses of the windings and the degree of heating of the active parts of the AM
d_{sp} and d_{rp}	Affects resistance, thermal regime and parasitic capacitances in the active part of the AM
b_r and b_s	Determines the current density of the windings, determines the dissipation losses, determines the resistance and inductance of the winding cores
h_r and h_s	
g	It has great importance for the entire electromagnetic state of the AM, determines the magnetizing current and moment of inertia
L_m	Determines the ability of the stator core to store magnetic energy

Taking into account the parameter vector p , we rewrite the system of flux linkage equations in AM:

$$\begin{cases} u_{sd} = R_s \cdot i_{sd} + \frac{d\psi_{sd}}{dt} - (\omega_{sl} + p \cdot \omega_m) \cdot \psi_{sq}, \\ u_{sq} = R_s \cdot i_{sq} + \frac{d\psi_{sq}}{dt} + (\omega_{sl} + p \cdot \omega_m) \cdot \psi_{sd}, \\ 0 = R_r \cdot i_{rd} + \frac{d\psi_{sr}}{dt} - (\omega_s - p \cdot \omega_m) \cdot \psi_{rq}, \\ 0 = R_r \cdot i_{rq} + \frac{d\psi_{rq}}{dt} + (\omega_s - p \cdot \omega_m) \cdot \psi_{rd}; \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where, ω_m – mechanical speed of the AM, Hz.

Having transformed the system of equations (1) taking into account (5) and (6), the multiparametric

$$\begin{cases} Z_s(\omega) = R_s + j \cdot \omega \cdot L_{\sigma s}, \\ Z_r(\omega, s) = \frac{R_r}{s} + j \cdot \omega \cdot L_{\sigma r}, \\ Z_m(\omega) = j \cdot \omega \cdot L_m \parallel R_c; \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

As a result of constructing the above mathematical apparatus, the multiparametric model of the electromagnetic moment of the AM in the coordinates ω and

model of the complex phase resistance of the AM will be obtained:

s , with parametric sensitivity, has the form shown in Fig. 1.

$$E_m = f(U_s, Z_s, Z_m) = \begin{cases} U_s = I_s \cdot Z_s + (Z_m \parallel Z_r), \\ Z_s = R_s + j \cdot \omega \cdot L_{\sigma s}, \\ Z_m = j \cdot \omega \cdot L_m; \end{cases} \quad \text{Multiparametric function component}$$

$$M_e(\omega, s) = \frac{3 \cdot p}{\omega_s} \cdot \frac{\frac{R_r}{s} \cdot |E_m|^2}{\left(\frac{R_r}{s}\right)^2 + (\omega \cdot L_{\sigma r})^2};$$

$$R_r(T, \omega) = \frac{l_{rp}}{\sigma_{cu}(T, \omega) \cdot d_{rp}} \cdot k_s(\omega) \cdot k_p(\omega); \quad \text{Multiparametric function component}$$

Fig. 1. Multiparametric mathematical model of the electromagnetic torque of an asynchronous electric motor

Fig. 1 shows:

E_m – EMF of the magnetic component of the electromagnetic system of the AM; l_{rp} – length of the rotor winding conductor (rod or turn), m; d_{rp} – diameter (or cross-sectional area) of the conductor, mm²; $k_s(\omega)$ – coefficient of increase in resistance due to the effect of current displacement, a.u.; $k_p(\omega)$ – coefficient of increase in resistance due to the effect of proximity (mutual influence of neighboring conductors) of conductors, a.u.

Having examined Figure 1 in detail, the following conclusions can be drawn regarding the obtained multiparametric mathematical model of an asynchronous electric motor, when using it in design work [8]:

- parameters located in the volume of the vector \mathbf{p} are included in the dq -equation using the resistances and inductance indices of the electromagnetic system of the AM, which are determined by the geometry, materials and frequency of the electromagnetic field;
- a stationary electromagnetic circuit of the AM with a slip allows you to model and obtain the operating

characteristics of the EM (such as current, torque, efficiency, etc.);

- the mechanical and electromagnetic parts of the multiparametric model are based on the multiphysical nature of the processes, which allows for the correction and optimization of efficiency and loss indicators, starting characteristics, and specific current indicators of the AM.

2. Implementation of the design method

In this section, we will perform multiparametric design of an asynchronous electric motor, the purpose of which is to determine the main geometric and structural parameters (for example, the number of slots, stator diameter and stator core length) and electromechanical and electromagnetic parameters (performance). To develop such an AM, we will use the provisions specified in [9].

Development object: asynchronous electric motor.

Initial data: power 18.5 kW, nominal speed 1500 rpm, mains voltage 220/380/660 V, frequency 50 Hz.

The design results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Results of designing an asynchronous electric motor

Параметр	Модель (описова частина):	Value type, and result
Productivity	$\begin{cases} P_{em} = \frac{P_2}{\eta \cdot \cos \varphi} \cdot \frac{E_{f1}}{U_n}, \\ P_{em} = m_1 \cdot U_n \cdot I_n \cdot \frac{\cos \varphi}{\cos \varphi_g}; \end{cases}$	Numerical: 18.5 kW
Rotation frequency	$n_2 = \frac{60 \cdot f_n}{p} \cdot (1 - s);$	Numerical: 1470 rpm (nominal)
Stator outer diameter	$D_1 = \sqrt{\frac{6.1 \cdot P_{em} \cdot 10^4}{\alpha_i \cdot k_\Phi \cdot k_0 \cdot A \cdot B_\delta \cdot n_2 \cdot l_1}};$	Numerical: 330 mm.
Stator core length	$l_1 = \frac{E_{f1} \cdot I_n \cdot p \cdot m_1}{k_\Phi \cdot k_0 \cdot f_n \cdot \pi^2 \cdot \alpha_i \cdot A \cdot B_\delta \cdot D^2};$	Numerical: 230 mm.
Number of stator and rotor slots	$z_1 = 6 \cdot p \cdot q_1; \quad z_2 = 4 \cdot p \cdot q_2;$	Integer: 48 stator 28 rotor

Rotor type	It is determined structurally: phase or squirrel-cage rotor type	Category: phase
Type of climatic design	Classification according to GOST 15150-69: U, UHL, TV, TS, T, O, M, TM, OM, V.	List: type selected – U
Structural design	Classification according to DSTU GOST 2479-79: IM101X, IM202X, IM301X, IM401X ...	List: selected – IM101X
Cooling type	Classification according to DSTU GOST 20459-87: IC01, IC06, IC411, IC416, IC410, IC37 ...	List: selected – IC411

Conclusion

From the results of Table 2 we have that the AM provides the required power at four-pole rotations – 1470 rpm, the dimensions of the stator core are in the standardized range of this EM class (330 × 230 mm), the number of rotor and stator slots also belongs to the recommended range of values: for the stator – 48 ... 72 slots, for the rotor – 28 ... 36 slots [10], in order to improve the starting torque and smooth speed control of the AM, the phase rotor type was selected, the climatic design type is moderate (U), the most unified design type is on the legs, with one or two bearing shields,

cooling is implemented using a built-in fan, in a closed housing, as well as with heat dissipation from the outside of the housing [11]. As a result of multiparametric design, the following possible AM design options were determined, which are given in Table 3. In our case, only option number 1 is suitable, because only it has a phase rotor with a minimum EM mass index and a relatively low rated current, the other three options only provide information about the adequacy and reliability of the results obtained by matching the received design information.

Table 3.

Options for selecting an asynchronous electric motor based on design results

№	Brand	Power, kW	Voltage, V	Rotation speed rpm	Rotor type	Efficiency %	cos φ	Hold, A	Weight kg
1	AIR-160M4	18,5	380	1500	Phasic	89,0	0,86	22,5	95
2	AIM160M4	18,5	380	1500	Phasic	90,0	0,86	36,3	162
3	AM160M4	18,5	380	1500	Short-circuited	90,0	0,86	36,3	162
4	5A160M4	18,5	380	1500	Phasic	90,0	0,86	34,7	150

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